

STUDY OF TYPES AND WORKING SCHEMES OF THYRISTOR FREQUENCY CONVERTERS

Ulug'murodov Elshod Abdusalim o'g'li

Student Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnics at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and agricultural Mechanization Engineers"
 ulugmurodovelshod2001@mail.ru

Najimov Javohir Zokir o'g'li

Student Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnics at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and agricultural Mechanization Engineers"

Turdiyev Botirbek Baxodir o'g'li

Student Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnics at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and agricultural Mechanization Engineers"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10118704>

Abstract. This article provides information about the principles of operation of thyristor frequency converters, connection schemes, the process of frequency generation using thyristors, and methods of controlling thyristors.

Key words: Thyristors, frequency generation, parallel connection of thyristors, thyristor control methods, thyristor circuits.

Access

In direct frequency converters with thyristors, the alternating current voltage with a constant frequency and the actual value of the voltage coming from the network is changed to an adjustable alternating current voltage without direct intermediate converters.

We will consider the principle of operation of direct TFC (Thyristor frequency converter) based on the single-phase scheme of this converter (Fig. 1). This circuit consists of a reversible zero circuit of a constant current thyristor converter. If we give a signal to the thyristors of the left group to open, the voltage from the load Z_{load} will have a positive sign relative to the zero point, and its average value will be $U_{load} = U_{load0} \cos F$, where the control angle of the thyristors; Load when U_{load0} steering angle is 0. Voltage at Z_{load} .

Fig 1. Circuit of single-phase direct TFC

Now when we open the thyristors of the right group by giving control signals, the thyristors of the left group close and the signal of the voltage on Z_{load} becomes negative. If we periodically send control pulses to the thyristors of this group, the sign of the load voltage will also change accordingly. Thus, we create an alternating voltage with a frequency different from (equal to or less than) the frequency of the network. By changing the sequence period of control pulses, the frequency of U_{load} is controlled, if we change the control angle, the average value of U_{load} is adjusted.

Three-phase zero circuits of direct TFCs are more often used in the electrical operations of industrial devices, and its principle scheme is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig 2. Three-phase zero-circuit indirect TFC circuit

The number of working thyristors is 18. The number of working thyristors is 36 in the three-phase bridge scheme version of the direct TFC (Fig. 3). The use of this scheme direct TFC in medium and high-power alternating current electric lines is justified by economic and operational indicators.

Phase shifting devices used in reversible DC converters are used to directly control the control angle of TFCs. In the working scheme of the direct TFC, depending on the number of sets of thyristors, there should be as many FSQs, that is, for direct TFCs with a three-phase zero scheme, the number of FSQs should be six. A six-phase symmetrical system with adjustable frequency and voltage amplitude should be used to control FSQs.

If the form of direct TFC output voltage is right-angled - stepped, then a six-phase "generator" producing a right-angled pulse is used as a controlled voltage source. Such a "generator" consists of single-phase generator and pulse distributor blocks.

Fig 3. Indirect TFC circuit with a three-phase bridge circuit

Summary

Thyristors are currently used to generate frequency, generate direct current, and adjust output power. When using thyristors, there are several types depending on their connection scheme. Thyristors are semiconductor devices based on monocrystalline silicon with electrical valve properties. A semiconductor element is made of a single crystal disk (plate) of silicon (with some boron, aluminum and phosphorus added). The principle of operation is based on the property of electron-hole transition (transition from electron p conductivity to hole r conductivity) of silicon single crystal. This property provides valved conductivity of the device. T. has triode (trinistor; three external outputs — cathode, anode, control electrode) and diode (dinistor, without control electrode) types. According to the function, it is divided into one-way and two-way conductive, high-frequency, pulsed, double-operation and special types. There are photoresistors, thyristors based on gallium arsenide. In conclusion, it should be said that by using thyristors, it is possible to achieve a number of achievements in the electrical power system and to save electricity.

References:

1. Осипов О.И. Частотно-регулируемый асинхронный электропривод.
2. Ключев В.И. Теория электропривода: Учебник для вузов. 2-е изд., перераб. и доп.М.: Энергоатомиздат, 1998. 704 с.
3. Суптель А.А. Асинхронный частотнорегулируемый электропривод: Учеб.пособие. Чебоксары: Изд-во Чуваш. ун-та, 2000. 164 с.
4. chistotnik.ru
5. Drives.ru
6. tes-privod.ru